

MEDICAL SCIENCES

INDICATIONS FOR THE USE OF THE ROOTS OF DECAYED TEETH FOR PROSTHETICS

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Abstract

The use of the roots of teeth destroyed by the carious process in dental prosthetics requires disinfection of the contents of the root canals after their mechanical and drug treatment. Disinfection is achieved by electrofulguration, which is accompanied by ozonation of the root canals. The use of the sparing methods proposed by us for preserving the roots of teeth during dental prosthetics, as studies have shown, allows us to preserve the roots of destroyed teeth and use them as a support for various designs of dentures.

Keywords: orthopedic dentistry, electrofulguration, microbiological, mathematical research, dental prosthetics, root preservation.

In recent years, much attention has been paid in dental practice to the development of less traumatic and sparing methods of treatment, especially in dental prosthetics. Caries, non-caries lesions, their complications and dental injuries often lead to complete or partial destruction of the crown part of the teeth and, as a result, to their removal.

According to some authors, 97% of the roots of the teeth can be restored or used as a support for subsequent prosthetics. However, only 2% use them in clinical practice [1].

The problem of maximum preservation of decayed teeth is of particular practical importance for the prevention of deformities of the dentition and atrophy of the alveolar processes. In addition, the preservation of decayed teeth will make it possible to avoid their removal with the ensuing consequences [2]. One of the main reasons for tooth extraction remains the problem associated with drug treatment and filling of root canals, especially those that are difficult to pass, as well as in the presence of cystogranulomas and other pathological processes in the tissues surrounding the tooth, which requires a balanced approach in their preparation for dental prosthetics.

Nevertheless, the practical experience of many specialists has proved the possibility of using the roots of teeth for dental prosthetics with fixed structures, subject to preliminary thorough preparation of their root canals. A number of methods for drug treatment of root canals and the most effective preparations for its implementation have been proposed, but positive results have not always been obtained [3]. Based on this, it should be considered appropriate to conduct further clinical and laboratory research to develop rational methods for preparing the roots of teeth for orthopedic treatment and improve the known ones in order to increase the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment of patients with

complete or partial defect of the crown part of the tooth.

Purpose of the study.

Increasing the efficiency of preserving the roots of teeth before dental prosthetics by developing the most effective method

root canal treatment and the choice of rational designs of prostheses, taking into account the masticatory load.

Material and research methods

In accordance with the set goal, we examined 203 patients, aged 24 to 56 years, who applied to the Department of Orthopedic Dentistry of the Kiev Medical University for orthopedic care. General characteristics of patients by age and gender are presented in Table. 1. A clinical examination showed the need for appropriate preparation of the roots of the teeth for dental prosthetics with the manufacture of rational orthopedic structures. At the same time, a complex examination scheme was used, as a result of which indications for the manufacture of pin structures were found. 143 patients (64 men and 79 women), whose clinical situation in the oral cavity allowed the use of pin structures, were taken for treatment. When examining patients admitted for treatment, the state of the masticatory apparatus and occlusion, occlusal contacts of the dentition on diagnostic models with movement analysis were studied lower jaw in an adjustable articulator; examined the movements of the lower jaw in the temporomandibular joints, the state of the masticatory muscles; X-ray examination of the jaws was performed (at the same time, the angle of inclination of the teeth and their roots towards the defect of the dentition was determined), as well as the temporomandibular joints, if necessary, a microbiological examination was performed. All patients underwent appropriate endodontic intervention

according to standard protocols, except for the main groups of observations, in

which, when finishing the root canals, electrofulguration was used [4] after necrotomy of the carious cavity,

instrumental processing and drying of root canals, introducing an electrode into a thin root canal not reaching the root tip by 0.5 mm and intermittent electric spark treatment for 10 seconds with an electric current at an interval of 5 seconds [5]

In patients of the main group I,

microbiological study of the content of the root

canal before and after electrosurgical treatment

The possibility of using the roots of teeth for dental prosthetics in case of complete destruction of their crown part, as well as in case of destruction in the area

bifurcation allowed to expand the indications for the use of fixed dentures in patients with defects in the dentition. To select an orthopedic design according to the proposed by us

In the clinic, we carried out a mechanical and mathematical modeling of the stress-strain state of the periodontium of such a tooth under the action of a masticatory load by way of compensation for a defect in the crown of a tooth with a destroyed bifurcation [6].

Research results and discussion

Our studies have shown that the majority of the roots (97.9%) of destroyed teeth can be saved and used for pin structures, as a support for fixed or removable dentures.

Prosthetics using the roots made it possible to more effectively restore the function of the dentoalveolar apparatus, since the prostheses, relying on the roots, made it possible to redistribute the masticatory load in a natural way through the periodontium. At the same time, adequate preparation of the roots of the teeth and their processing became important.

root canals for dental prosthetics. It was the infection of the latter in a complicated carious process with localization in the periapical tissues that caused the removal of teeth and the appearance of

deformations of the dentition Thus, during the microbiological study of the contents of the root canals,

the following microorganisms: *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Enterococcus casseliflavus*, *Streptococcus mitis*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Streptococcus milleri*,

Gemella haemolysans, *Haemophilus* (*Actinobacillus*) *actinomycetemcomitans*, *Aerococcus viridans*, *Actinomyces viscosus*, *Prevotella melaninogenica*,

Capnocytophaga spp., *Veillonella* spp.

The conducted studies showed that after electrosurgical treatment of root canals, the growth of microflora was not observed. All cultures were sterile [7].

The mechanical and mathematical modeling of the stress-strain state of the periodontium was carried out and showed that the maximum normal stresses significantly exceed the contiguous stresses in their magnitude, and this phenomenon is especially noticeable when

large angles of inclination of the chewing force relative to the axis of the tooth root. Therefore, at angles of inclination of the masticatory effort of more than 15°, in order to preserve such teeth, it is necessary to

limit the chewing component, which is directed in the vestibulo-lingual direction.

Conclusions

The use of the roots of teeth destroyed by the carious process in dental prosthetics requires their appropriate and adequate preparation, and first of all, disinfection of the contents of the root canals after their mechanical and drug treatment,

which was confirmed by the data of ongoing microbiological and clinical studies.

The use of electrofulguration, accompanied by ozonation of the root canals, makes it possible to ensure their disinfection, and in the presence of cystogranules and granulation tissues around the roots in the area of the destroyed bifurcation, destruction with dry soft tissue necrosis.

Based on the mechanical and mathematical modeling of the stress-strain state of the periodontium and the calculations, it was found that at the angles of inclination of the masticatory force more

15 ° to save teeth that have undergone orthopedic treatment, it is necessary to limit the chewing force component directed in the vestibular-lingual direction. The use of the sparing methods we proposed for preserving the roots of teeth during dental prosthetics, as studies have shown, allows you to save the roots of destroyed teeth and use them as supports of various designs of dentures.

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